

MEN'S MANUAL TO MEN'S SUPPORT GROUPS

Manual dedicated to moderators of support groups for refugee men from Arabic and Tigrinya speaking regions

In collaboration with

× Gemeente
× Amsterdam

FOREWORD

This manual is made by the Department of Ethics, Law & Humanities/ section of Participation and Diversity of Amsterdam UMC, in collaboration with Doctors of the World. This manual is part of the Men's Project (project ID: 2011292), subsidized by the City of Amsterdam.

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Table of contents

Introduction

The points to be reported by the moderator after each session

The conversation rules suggested by the advisory boards (RvA)

The tools to be prepared by the moderator before each session

The (imaginary) characters of Yonas and Sami

Theme 1. Identity

Theme 2. Safety

Theme 3. Diversity

Theme 4. Discrimination

Theme 5. Management of anger and sadness

Theme 6. Social responses/ Gender roles

Introduction

Amsterdam UMC, in collaboration with Doctors of the World (*Dokters van de Wereld*), started “the men project” in September 2022. The project includes creating support groups for men with refugee backgrounds from Syria and Eritrea in three housing locations in Amsterdam. The setup of these support groups includes inviting men to sit together and to discuss themes and challenges with each other. We aim to support men through involving them to support each other, so that unnecessary (health) problems can be prevented. The reason is that life for newcomers in the Netherlands can be tough and burdened with many challenges. Sharing relevant experiences with other men contributes to strengthening mutual support among young men as well as establishing positive coping strategies with traumatic events, which in turn reduce mental problems. Each session of the peer support group represents one theme, with a total of six themes/sessions. During these sessions, participants may ask their own questions to the moderator, who may provide them with information, guidance and contact details of certain organizations that offer services for men with refugee backgrounds. The project team hopes to strengthen the connection between men through shared experiences and peer support.

The themes of the manual are chosen and designed based on the semi-structured interviews we conducted as part of our men’s project. These interviews discussed, among others, the issues of (masculine) identity, (barriers to) integration and (gender and sexual based) violence. In addition to the interviews, we were supported by two advisory boards (*raad van advies*); one had 4 Arabic speaking members and the other had 3 Tigrinya speaking members. The members of these boards are also refugee men in the Netherlands from Arabic and Tigrinya speaking countries. They were recruited by the project team based on their experiences, contributions and contact with their communities. By having four meetings through the period of the project, the main task of the advisory boards was to provide the main researcher with advice and recommendations with regard to:

- The themes to be discussed in the sessions
- The relevance of the cases and the questions in each session
- The conversation rules to be followed during the sessions
- The set up of each session
- The methods of approaching men in the housing locations to participate in the sessions
- The content of the brochure and social media texts used by Doctors of the World to invite prospect participants in the sessions

Moreover, two moderators (*gespreksleiders*) were recruited by Doctors of the World to facilitate the sessions. Both moderators were members of the advisory boards; one Arabic speaking to facilitate the support groups for Syrian men, and one Tigrinya speaking to facilitate the support groups for Eritrean men. Here, it is pertinent to mention that the language used in this manual addresses the moderators as the following: *You are there to facilitate the sessions, to lead the conversation, to introduce the cases and activities to participants. In addition, you facilitate the sessions through engaging participants and encouraging them to listen to each other and to support the process of exchange. You will use your mother tongue to communicate with*

participants and listen to them rather than participating with your experiences and examples. Each participant may decide the questions he wants to answer and the exercises he wants to do. Participants may also talk a little longer or shorter about a certain topic. At the end of each session, the moderator is asked to report how the session went in terms of the following points.

The points to be reported by the moderator after each session

- The structure of the session: duration and break timing
- The material: were the tools/ exercises/ games/ videos helping? Or too dry?
- The engagement of participants with the topic: answering and asking question
- The story (case): Relevant? Familiar?
- The dynamic of the group: communication with each other, reacting to the moderator
- The most remarkable moment/ comment/ answer/ notice during the session
- Things/ questions/ parts of the story.. etc to be adjusted
- General thoughts/ notes.

The conversation rules suggested by the advisory boards (RvA)

- We keep everything here confidential: everything stays in this space.
- We accept and respect each other's differences (in opinions, experiences and tastes).
- We don't judge each other or evaluate their experiences.
- We listen carefully to each other's stories and open the space to anyone who wants to share something.
- You can say anything you want as long as it stems from your genuine respect and interest, and does not violate any other rule.
- You can always ask questions.
- Telling your own experience should be stemming from recognition or difference with what you hear from others, not from judgment.
- You don't give unsolicited advice unless you are clearly asked to.
- Recognize that sharing personal stories is brave and exciting, so we honor that with thanking and asking relevant questions.
- Please put phones on 'silent'.

The tools to be prepared by the moderator before each session

- Yonas and Sami characters' descriptions and photos
- The case of each session printed on paper to be distributed to participants
- Playlist with Arabic/ Eritrean music for the breaks (YouTube list in which participants can add music)
- Coffee/tea, snacks
- Pens and pieces of paper (or possibly small notebooks)
- Flip charts
- Conversation rules (written on a flip chart)
- Laptop with Wi-Fi

- (Foot)-ball (only for the first session)

The (imaginary) characters of Yonas and Sami

The Syrian Yonas (left) and Sami (right), credits: @haddouchi_visual

The Eritrean Yonas (left) and Sami (right), credits: @aristry_by_ruti

Yonas is a 29 years old Syrian/Eritrean guy who moved to the Netherlands in 2018. He lives alone in Amsterdam and feels like a stranger due to many difficulties. He is still busy with his integration process and he does not have many friends. Yonas could not finish his studies in

Syria/Eritrea but he learnt to work as a barber until he can enroll in a university program when his skills in Dutch language are good enough.

Sami is a 35 years-old accountant who fled Syria/ Eritrea in 2016 and he lives now with his wife and their 3 year-old child in Amsterdam. He went through a lot of suffering when he was in Syria/ Eritrea and it was not easy for him in the Netherlands either. His relationship to his wife is burdened with many issues and sometimes they end up in fights with each other. However, both of them completed the courses and exams required for their civic integration. Eventually, Sami found a job as an accountant but he does not actually have Dutch friends.

Sami and Yonas know each other from Syria/ Eritrea where Sami used to work in Yonas' father's workshop. However, they never visited each other in Amsterdam because Yonas lives in a little space whereas Sami is always busy with his family.

Theme 1. Identity

The setup of the session (120 minutes)

- Introducing the project (5 minutes)
- Name game: Getting to know each other (10 minutes)
- Activity 1: Elements of identity (15 minutes)
- Case (45 minutes)
- Break (10 minutes)
- Activity 2: Photo meaning (15 minutes)
- Closing with the conversation rules (20 minutes)

Aims of the session

- Establishing trust by getting to know the project and each other
- Establishing the connection and differences between personal identities and collective identities.
- Emphasizing that adjustment to a new culture and changes in identity can merge after migration.

Preparation for participants

Ask each participant to bring/ prepare a photo of him when he was in his home country, a photo that means a lot to him (photograph or on his phone).

Introducing the project (5 minutes)

Explain to the participants that we meet today to get to know each other, to have fun together but also to talk about men's lives in the Netherlands. Tell them that the content of the sessions is created through scientific research, and that the sessions are part of a collaboration project between Amsterdam UMC and Doctors of the World. Explain shortly that this project is funded through the municipality of Amsterdam, and that it addresses men's issues and offers a listening ear to what they are going through. Also, mention the possibility of asking questions about health and well-being so that you can refer participants to the program Zorg Café.

Name game (10 minutes)

The first member of the group announces his name. Then the second member of the group repeats the first person's name and adds his own, the third person says the names of the first and second person and adds his own, and so on around the group. Afterwards, use a ball and throw it to someone in the group saying his name, and ask him to throw it to someone else saying his name, and so on until all names are recalled.

Activity 1: Elements of identity (15 minutes)

Tell the participants that identity is the mixture of values, beliefs, behavior, expressions, skills and qualities, attitude and appearance that makes us who we are, personally as individuals and collectively as a group. Add that identities guide behavior, leading men to behave like men, and teachers to act like teachers. Based on that, ask each participant to write down two elements of

his identity; one that he thinks is unique to him, and one he thinks he shares with everyone in the group. The aim of this activity is to affirm that elements of identity are diverse and can be both personal and collective: we can have both, our personal identity and our collective identity. Examples of identity elements: name, gender, sex, race, profession, relationship status, religion, beliefs, sexual orientation, family, nationality, hobbies, skills, physical appearance, etc.

Case (45 minutes)

Tell the participants that every time we meet, there will be a short story about the imaginary characters of Yonas and Sami. Explain that we start with the description of Yonas' and Sami's characters. You can find these in the introduction to this manual. Be aware not to give more information about Yonas and Sami than what is already mentioned in the description.

Afterwards, distribute the story printed on paper to the participants and ask them to read it before you start asking the questions.

Sami invited Yonas to his place where his wife made delicious Syrian/Eritrean dinner. "We don't have many friends visiting because most of them are busy with establishing a new life here", said Sami. Yonas replied that he is also trying to learn Dutch at school. "But the Dutch language is difficult and things are more complicated than at home", said Yonas. Sami agreed and added that other issues like discrimination make him feel invisible. "We are not the same strong Syrian/Eritrean men anymore", said Yonas sarcastically. After dinner, Sami told Yonas about his new job; "It's nice here that there is a job for everyone". Yonas said that he cannot wait to become an architect. "If only I speak good Dutch", said Yonas. "This is because you use your Arabic/Tigrinya and English in the barbershop. If I were you, I would use Dutch instead". Yonas does not like to be advised so he said "I will do my best to become an architect". At the end, Yonas thanked Sami for the invitation saying that it reminded him of these nights in their home country. "I miss it a lot", said Sami.

- What did you take with you when you left your home country? Why?
- What is it like for you to find work or study in the Netherlands?
- What were your expectations about life here before you came? How was it in reality?
- What did you lose/miss as a man since you moved to the Netherlands?
- What are the advantages of living here for you as a Syrian/Eritrean man?
- What is the biggest change you went through after moving here? How do you feel about this change?
- What do you think Yonas meant when he said "we are not as strong as before"?
- Sami mentioned that racism and discrimination make him feel invisible. What do you think he meant?
- Yonas does not like to be advised. What else men like Yonas do not like?
- Do you show other people here who you really are? Why?
(examples include wearing your national costumes or celebrating your national events)
- What has helped you to overcome the challenges you went through at the beginning here?
- What are your tips for a man who is struggling with establishing his new life here?
- Yonas wants to be an architect. What about you? How do you reach your goal?

Break (10 minutes)

Activity 2: Photo meaning (15 minutes)

Ask the participants to use the photos they brought to the session. Each participant has 2 minutes to say something about his photo: What is it? Why have you chosen it? What does it mean to you? Focus on what makes each participant unique and what brings all participants together. Confirm the elements of identity and the cultural characteristics they share.

Closing with the conversation rules (20 minutes)

Suggest establishing conversation rules for the next sessions based on the interaction that took place in this session. Ask the participants about the rules they find important and integrate their answers with the rules suggested by the advisory board (RvA) in the introduction of this manual. Write the final set of conversation rules on the flip chart and keep it for the next sessions. Thank the participants for joining and tell them then ask them (informally) about their feedback.

Theme 2. Safety

The setup of the session (~1.5 hours)

- Introduction (10 minutes)
- Activity 1: Brainstorming (15 minutes)
- Case (45 minutes)
- Activity 2: Unsafe moment (20 minutes)
- Closing (10 minutes)

Aims of the session

- Emphasizing the types of personal and social safety that refugee men might go through
- Explaining that past and current experiences with unsafety could lead to distrust, mental health issues and negative social attitudes
- Encouraging the participating men to share and acknowledge their experiences with being unsafe

Introduction (10 minutes)

Name game: Use the (foot)-ball and throw it to someone in the group saying his name, then ask him to throw it to someone else saying his name, and so on until all names are recalled.

Afterwards, introduce the project briefly as you did in the first session. This is to remind participants of what we are doing as well as to inform any participant who was not in the first session. Here you can show the conversation rules written on the flip chart in order to keep them during the sessions.

Activity 1: Brainstorming (15 minutes)

Tell the participants that today's topic is about safety. Ask them to brainstorm what safety means for them, from who or what one needs to be safe. Write their answers on the flip-chart and encourage them to mention all types of safety they can come up with. Keep the flip chart to inspire the participants later in the case.

Next, explain that in addition to what someone might do to protect himself, there is also social safety, which includes all actions, policies and programs designed to reduce poverty and vulnerability. This is done through promoting efficient labor markets, diminishing people's exposure to risks, and enhancing their capacity to manage economic, health, and social risks, such as unemployment, exclusion, sickness, disability and old age.

Case (45 minutes)

Remind the participants of the description and pictures of Yonas and Sami, then distribute the case printed on paper to each participant to read it.

Sami knew that Yonas was very sick so he went to check up on him. There, Sami noticed that the building was noisy and not as clean as he supposed. "Yeah the building is crowded with young residents and many of them are in trouble with the law", said Yonas. "This would not help you to recover or to study later. Yonas agreed and told Sami about an incident that made him

feel really unsafe. "This is a lot! Sometimes a report about discrimination or crime in the news makes me worried about the safety of my family, but I keep contact with my neighbors to feel safer", said Sami. Yonas said that he is afraid to make connections, neither with his Dutch neighbors nor with those from his home country. "It is very difficult to feel secure and safe outside one's home. This brings a lot of stress", said Sami.

- What types of safety do you find in the story?
- What would you do if you were in Yonas' shoes? Keep contact with your neighbors or not? Why?
- Is being safe in the Netherlands similar to being safe in your home country? Why yes/no? Examples?
- Why do you think that safety for a Dutch neighbor is different from safety for you?
- Do you fear getting in danger for saying what you think or believe in? Why?
- Do you think that money can buy safety? Why yes/no?
- Sami mentioned stress. What are the other consequences of feeling unsafe?
- If you could change one thing in your life/surrounding in order to feel safer, what would it be? Why?
- What is your advice to Syrian/Eritrean men in NL to feel safer?
- What is your most important source of safety? How do you reach it?

Activity 2: unsafe moment (20 minutes)

Ask the participants who would like to tell the group (in two minutes) about a time he felt unsafe in the Netherlands? Why was that? What did he do? What would he do differently?

Closing (10 minutes)

Explain that the next meeting will be about diversity. For that session, ask participants to bring a photo (on their phones) of someone who they think is very different from them. This person could be:

- Someone with a different religious background.
- Someone from a different country or culture.
- Someone with a different gender expression.
- Someone with different political views.
- Someone with a different skin color.
- Someone with different sexual orientation.

Theme 3. Diversity

The set up of the session (1.5 hours)

Activity 1: Diversity homework (20 minutes)

Case (45 minutes)

Activity 2: Look in the mirror (20 minutes)

Closing (5 minutes)

Aims of the session

- To promote multiculturalism in refugee men's communities, as a diverse society functions better.
- To address social isolation many refugee men suffer from
- To inspire individuals who are different from others how to work together effectively
- To facilitate positive intergroup interaction

Activity 1: Diversity homework (20 minutes)

Remind the participants that you asked them to bring a photo (that could also be from the internet) of someone who they think is very different from them. This person could be:

- Someone with a different religious background.
- Someone from a different country or culture.
- Someone with a different gender expression.
- Someone with different political views.
- Someone with a different skin color.
- Someone with different sexual orientation.

The aim of this activity is to evoke who the participants consider as the "other", and to let them think thoroughly about what makes this person an "other" for them, before introducing them to the concept of diversity.

Ask the participants: Why did you choose this person in particular? Why do you think he is different from you? What do you usually think about these differences? Do you have people like him in your life? How is your relationship with them?

Afterwards, ask the participants: What does diversity mean for you? Here you may write the keywords they suggest on the flipchart and keep it til the end of the session.

Case (45 minutes)

Yonas and Sami decided to go together to the gym. "There are all kinds of people in the gym, unlike my classmates at the language course, they are all Syrians/Eritreans. I find it hard to trust my classmates, especially that some might have principles and lifestyle contrary to those of me. However, I like it that we can help each other in our mother tongue when the lesson is difficult". Said Yonas while they were training. "Definitely you have differences and similarities but luckily that is always the case. What about meeting people from other cultures?" Asked Sami. Yonas answered that he is not very much interested in that. "I am from another culture and I speak a different language. I don't find many people who want to meet me either. Why should I do that then?" Sami replied that it is a mutual effort and one should do his part. "Sooner or later you will

hang out with people from other parts of the world. You tend to create obstacles while they do not exist”.

- What do you think of this conversation between Yonas and Sami?
- Who do you agree with more? Yonas or Sami? Why?
- What do you think of what Yonas said about people not wanting to meet him?
- What are your experiences with that, in the language school, at the gym or at work?
- What do you think about Yonas finding excuses to stay away from people different from him?
- Is it hard for you, like Yonas, to make use of the diversity of Dutch society? Why or why not?
- What do you do to be approachable by others, especially those different from you?
- What was a nice moment for you dealing with someone different from you?

Activity 2: Look in the mirror (20 mins)

Ask each participant who wants to do this exercise: What would you tell us about the person you are? Imagine that you are looking at yourself as another person, an outsider perspective of yourself. What would you say about the person you see?

Here, you may start with yourself as a facilitator to show the participants an example so that they follow. You may talk about two or three characteristics/ experiences/ achievements that make you unique. The aim of this exercise is to show that no matter how similar we are to each other, there are differences that make our experiences more diverse and unique.

Closing (5 minutes)

Affirm that people have similarities and differences, in terms of culture, political views, religious beliefs, sexual orientation, gender expression, socio-economic situation and so on. Build on the positive experiences with diversity that were mentioned in the session, and tell the participants that:

- Diversity is about what makes each of us unique and includes all of the things that make us who we are, such as communication style, career path, life experience, educational background, geographic location, income level, marital status, parental status and other variables that influence personal perspectives.
- Being different within your family, surrounding, neighborhood, work or society is a feature to cherish and a motivation to be authentic to who you are, and so is the case for everyone else.
- Diversity drives creativity and innovation because we can all learn something and grow by listening to people with different experiences, perspectives, and backgrounds than us.
- Every culture, every nationality, every single person sees the world in a different way, and that is very valuable and important.

Finally, ask the participants to reflect on today's session and to think of the person in the photo they brought to the first activity, as a reflection of diversity in the world.

Theme 4. Discrimination

The set up of the session (1.5 hours)

Activity 1: Grounds of discrimination (15 minutes)

Case (45 minutes)

Activity 2: Experiencing discrimination (25 mins)

Closing (5 minutes)

Aims of the session:

- To delineate the broad sense of discrimination, its types and effects
- To discuss discrimination experiences in and outside the community of male refugees
- To strengthen healing process through sharing experiences
- To provide participants with the information needed to report discrimination

Activity 1: Grounds of discrimination (15 minutes)

Start the session by telling the participants that today we are going to talk about discrimination, which is *the unfair treatment of people and groups based on certain characteristics*. Ask participants the following question: *What do you think these characteristics might be?*

Write their answers on the flipchart, then add any ground of discrimination that was not mentioned. The following are the grounds of discrimination specified by the Dutch law:

race/ sex/ hetero- or homosexual orientation/ political opinion/ religion/ belief/ disability or chronic illness/ civil status/ age/ nationality/ working hours (full time or part time)/ type of contract (temporary or permanent).

Note: if racism was mentioned as a form of discrimination, tell the participants that discrimination has a broader sense than racism: racism is a form of prejudice towards a racial group whereas racial discrimination is practicing this prejudice and it is just one type of discrimination.

Conclude the exercise with telling the participants that everyone in the Netherlands is entitled to equal treatment. This right is considered so important that it is enshrined in Article 1 of the Dutch Constitution. By collecting all possible perceptions of discrimination thought by participants, the aim of this exercise is to affirm that discrimination is not limited to one aspect. This overview would launch the session with an understanding of the broad spectrum of potential experiences to be shared throughout the session.

Case (45 minutes)

Sami went to the barbershop where Yonas works to get a new haircut. Yonas was busy with another guy who was telling a story: “.. he dresses oddly and I can’t tolerate him living next door. How can he be Sy/Er like us?” Whereas Yonas had not commented, Sami blamed him later for saying nothing. “You just accepted a clear incident of discrimination despite your recent experience with covert discrimination”. Yonas replied that he is still confused whether it was covert discrimination when he had an incident at the train station. “This confusion is a common effect of discrimination. You also tried to defy your community and this is because you felt attacked due to your identity. Didn’t you?”. “Maybe yes”, Yonas answered.

- What do you think of this conversation between Yonas and Sami?
- What would you do if you were in Yonas' situation with the other guy?
- What do you think Sami meant by "covert discrimination"?
- Do you agree with Sami that covert discrimination makes one feel confused and defies his community? Why?
- How can you tell if you have been discriminated against?
- Why do you think a SY/ER man in NL might be discriminated against?
- What are your experiences with (covert) discrimination in the Netherlands?
- How do you deal with such experiences?
- What do you do to fight discrimination?

Activity 2: Experiencing discrimination (25 mins)

Ask participants to make two groups then ask each group to write down a list of the effects of discrimination on one's social life, integration and mental health. After ten minutes of group discussions, let each group choose a participant to read what they wrote out loud, and write the keywords they come with on the flipchart. Afterwards, you add the effects that were not mentioned:

- A sense of being an "outsider" from the community.
- Perception of self as "less than" or "something is wrong."
- Pressure to represent one's community and to defy stereotypes.
- Experience of anxiety, depression, anger, and a sense of helplessness.
- Feeling confused about whether what you experienced was discrimination or not.
- At times you may experience physical symptoms, including decreased sleep quality, change of appetite, and sense of fatigue.

Closing (5 minutes)

Tell the participants that discrimination and prejudice can be overt, and at times take a covert (subtle) form, and that any form of discrimination, big or small, overt or subtle, is not okay and cannot be accepted or tolerated. Finally, emphasize that when being discriminated against, you might want to speak out or complain, but you are not sure how to go about it. Here are some tips:

- Take care of yourself and focus on what makes you strong and your core values
- Seek support from family and friends to remind you of your worth
- Seek professional help, such as the national discrimination helpline ([0900 235 4354](tel:09002354354))¹
- Help yourself think clearly through breathing techniques, which also help to manage any physiological response, especially that discrimination triggers sadness and anger.

Conclude that the next session is going to be about the management of sadness and anger.

¹ <https://www.government.nl/topics/discrimination/reporting-discrimination>

Theme 5. Management of anger and sadness

The set up of the session: (2 hours)

Activity 1: Hero in the movie (30 minutes)

Case (40 minutes)

Break (10 minutes)

Activity 2: Hard feelings (30 minutes)

Closing (10 minutes)

Aims of the session:

- To distinguish between having sadness and anger feelings and the way of expressing them among men
- To emphasize that suppressing feelings does not work on the long term and that is not healthy
- To help men explore new ways of channeling their feelings, constructively rather than destructively

Activity 1: Hero in the movie (30 minutes)

Welcome the participants and tell them that today's meeting is about the management of anger and sadness. Tell them that the nature of social interaction with others in society makes men face difficulties in dealing with certain feelings, such as anger and sadness. Emphasize that we are not here to criticize the way men interact socially, but to look into the impact of that on men. Ask the participants to write down 3-4 characteristics they attribute to the ideal man. To help them brainstorming, you may ask the following questions:

- What do heroes in movies from your culture look like?
- What is the social image/ expectations of the ideal man in your culture?
- What are the values that men strive to show?

Write the keywords of their answers on the flipchart, then based on that, discuss the following questions with the participants:

- To which degree can men always be strong without feeling fear or sadness? Is it fair?
- How do other men in society look at men who do not fit in the image of the ideal man?
- What are the potential consequences on men's mental health?

Here you may mention how men are allowed to show anger but not allowed to show sadness because it is a sign of weakness. Afterwards, tell the participants that we will explore this topic more in the case.

Case (40 minutes)

While Sami and Yonas were hanging out together walking their bicycles, Yonas received a phone call and he started to shout. After he hung up, he kicked his bicycle impulsively until it fell down. Sami carried the bicycle and said that what just happened was not okay. Yonas ignored that and said that he is going to "teach him a lesson". Sami did not know the person that Yonas wanted to teach a lesson to. "I understand that you feel angry for a reason but you cannot react to your anger like that", said Sami and gave Yonas a bottle of water to drink. After a long and

loud conversation, Sami succeeded eventually in calming Yonas who seemed very sad and turned silent. Although Yonas did not say how sad he was, Sami noticed and asked no more questions.

- What do you think Yonas meant by “teach him a lesson”? Why would a man say so?
- How do men react to other men when they have a conflict? Is it different from their reactions to women in similar situations? How do men react to women in conflicts?
- Why do you think Yonas tended to be violent when he got angry?
- Sami gave Yonas a bottle of water to calm him down. Would that calm you down when you get angry? What else would work for you when you feel angry?
- Why do you think Sami reacted when Yonas was angry but said nothing when Yonas was sad? Why did it seem unnatural for Sami to ask about what makes Yonas sad?
- Is being angry as a man different than as a woman? How? Why do you think so?
- Is being angry with someone younger different than with someone older? How? Why?
- How do you deal with your anger? Violently like Yonas or quieter like Sami? (destructively or constructively?)
- Who is the angriest person in your family/surrounding? What do you do to embrace (help them to process) their anger?
- How do you express being sad as a man? What do you do?
- What is the impact of accepting anger and ignoring sadness on one’s (mental) health?
- How do you think that beating others or breaking things are destructive ways of expressing anger?
- What are the constructive ways of dealing with anger?

Break (10 minutes)

Activity 2: Hard feelings (30 minutes)

Ask each of the participants to name one feeling he found difficult to express, what he did instead, what he would do differently, and how he feels about that now. Tell the participants that each has a maximum of 5 minutes to answer, to ensure that a space is available for anyone who wants to share. Listen to their answers and discuss them based on the points shared in the session.

Closing (10 minutes)

The takeaway message of today’s session: We are not the hero in the movie.

Use what the participants discussed in the session and the points below to make a conclusion:

- You are a human being, full of emotions and feelings, and that is wonderful.
- There is a difference between the feeling and the way we express that feeling. Anger and sadness are natural feelings, while expressing them can be either positive or negative, constructive or destructive.
- We all feel anger from time to time and that it is not a destructive feeling. Instead, the way of expressing anger might be destructive, such as breaking things or hurting people.
- We all feel sadness sometimes and it is not a sign of weakness. It helps us to grieve what we lost and to heal if we express it properly. Women manage sadness more easily

because they are not pressured not to cry, whereas men are socially pressured to suppress their sadness, which leads to other health problems.

- Because impulsiveness is the only socially accepted reaction of an angry man, it turns potentially into violence. Although it might help to relieve anger in the short term, it has a very negative impact on women, children or any person who depends on you. Most importantly, it has a negative impact on you.
- Intense feelings, such as anger and sadness, will always find a way to show up. Suppressing them for a long time gets them out of control. Therefore, we should find a way to channel them, such as expressing within the self, if not to someone else.
- We need to feel anger sometimes because it provokes positive changes, such as taking the initiative and fighting oppression.
- We always think of anger as a feeling that we cannot control, but actually we can when we learn to choose how to express anger depending on each situation.

Afterwards, thank the participants and tell them that the next session is the last one and it is going to be about the different social responses between men and women.

Theme 6. Social responses/ Gender roles

The setup of the session: (2 hours)

Activity 1: Who faces what (40 minutes)

Break (10 minutes)

Case: (45 minutes)

Activity 2 (15 minutes)

Closing with feedback (10 minutes)

Aims of the session

- To establish the link between the change of social circumstances and the adaptation of gender roles.
- To help men see the bigger picture of gender roles, where women are also main players.
- To emphasize that men also could also benefit from social changes to become more able to be engaged positively.

Important to note: *Gender roles are the behaviors learned by a person as appropriate to their gender, determined by the prevailing cultural norms. This topic leads potentially to long arguments. Therefore, the moderator has to keep the focus on the core message. Challenging predefined gender roles does not mean that each man has to do what women do or vice versa, but these options exist to those who want to adopt it. It is important to remember that gender roles are not fixed, and that flexibility is needed in this regard especially after forced migration.*

Disclaimer: *Gender roles are usually centered on conceptions of masculinity and femininity, although there are other variations, such as the non-binary and genderqueer that are outside the gender binary of male and female. Yet, we designed this session, and eventually the manual, to address heterosexual cis men as they are the expected beneficiaries of the support groups. We are not predefining cis-heterosexuality as eligibility criteria to participate in the support groups. However we expect that non-binary and genderqueer people would not join the groups, where most participants are cis-gender and heterosexual. This is mainly because of the long history of oppression that those people went through due to the dominant cis-and-heterosexual norms in their home countries. We think that support groups dedicated for non-binary and genderqueer refugees are needed in a separate context and setup, where the themes are also different, in order to address the issues of this community.*

Activity 1: Who faces what (40 minutes)

Divide the group into two; ask the first one to discuss the needs and problems faced by Sy/Er men. Ask the second group to discuss the needs and problems faced by Sy/Er women (in general). You may suggest that they can structure their discussions according to two contexts: before and after the flights. Give the participants 10 minutes to discuss the topics separately. Afterwards, each group can choose one participant or more to present the outcome. Then, you may indicate that each group can add what they think the other group missed. The core message of this activity is emphasizing that there are similarities and differences between the

needs and problems of each gender. In addition, it is important to understand that we can help and support each other as a society because we live together with our different needs.

- Examples of issues faced by men before the flight: the responsibility of being the breadwinner for the family, as well as being expected to express no feelings but anger.
- Examples of issues faced by men after the flight: the difficulty of building connections and having to stay more at home with the family.
- Examples of issues faced by women before the flight: the responsibility of raising and taking care of children, and having less space to have their own time.
- Examples of issues faced by women after the flight: having to contribute to the family's income, by finding a job for instance.

After listening to each group and discussing the core message of the activity, tell the participants that we will explore the topic more in the case after the break.

Break (10 minutes)

Case: (45 minutes)

Sami invited Yonas for a dinner made by him. "I had never seen you cooking back in Sy/Er!", wondered Yonas. Sami replied that yes, he started to cook sometimes, and that Leila, his wife, is very happy with that. "Sami spends more time with his son in addition to cooking. I started a part-time job", said Leila. Sami didn't seem very happy with the new changes, and said "I miss the old days when I used to spend hours away from home". Yonas told them that he could not imagine that moving to another country would change Sami.. "But we all had to change in a way or another, otherwise I can't do this alone", said Leila. Eventually, everyone complimented Sami's cooking. "It is not bad after all", said Yonas.

- Why do you think that men do not usually cook in Sy/Er? Who decided that?
- Why do you think that Sami, unlike Leila, was not happy about starting to cook and to look after his son?
- Yonas is single. How do you think his social responses changed between Sy/Er and the Netherlands?
- What are the responsibilities of Sy/ Er men in Syria/Eritrea? What were yours?
- What are the new responsibilities you started to take as a man in the Netherlands? How did you end up doing that? How do you feel about it?
- What are the things that men need to learn now, that was not necessary before?
- What are the other changes that would help family members to support each other in the host country? How?

During the discussions, you may emphasize the following points:

- Men and women play different roles depending on the society they live within.
- These gender roles are inherited in each society but they are not fixed and can vary from family to family in the same society.
- The change to gender roles happens due to external social factors or reasons that are out of our control, such as conflicts and immigration.

- Adapting gender roles to new social circumstances is necessary to help the family navigate the emerging challenges in the new society.
- Letting go of few social responsibilities and developing new ones require a lot of courage because we are used and attached to the old roles.
- Adapting gender roles does not mean abandoning all traditions and beliefs. Instead, adapting the traditions is needed due to the emergence of new social settings.

Activity 2: (15 minutes)

Ask each of the participants to identify (in 2 minutes max each):

- One response he would do to reduce his own burden/ negative feeling of responsibility?
- One response he would do, as a man, to reduce the burden of women (in general)?

Closing with feedback (10 minutes)

Affirm the core message of today's session, that changing social circumstances necessitates adapting the gender roles of both men and women to help each other navigate the emerging challenges. Emphasize that it is beneficial for men as well because it does not restrict them to the conventional gender roles that are, in some cases, unfair.

Afterwards, inform the participants that this is the last session and thank them for their time and active participation. Tell them that the last thing they need to provide is their feedback about the sessions. Ask them to use a paper to write (anonymously) their ideas about the support group.

You may also ask questions, such as:

- One or two positive points about today's meeting
- One or two negative points about today's meeting
- How do you find being in a peer group

Collect all the papers in a box but without reading any of them. Discuss it with the organizers later. If a participant asks a question that is related directly to one thematic session, answer him briefly and explain that we will go through this conversation later in future sessions.